

**A MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR
PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASE OF EDUCATIONAL VALUES**

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Abstract: The article describes the pedagogical possibilities of forming the attitude of tolerance in preschool children. It is also required to determine the forms and technological peculiarities of tolerance education. It is necessary to inculcate the fact that tolerance is a high-level human virtue in the minds of the young generation from the first stages of education.

Key words: preschool education, tolerance, perfect person, tolerance, love of peace, patriotism, culture, young generation, educator.

Today, fundamental improvement of the regulatory legal framework in the field of preschool education in our republic, integration of advanced foreign experiences, scientific developments and technology into the activities of preschool educational institutions, support of scientific and innovative pedagogical activities in the field of early development of preschool children. conceptual reforms aimed at support are being implemented. The culture of behavior formed in our people, the feelings related to manners, such as kindness, kindness, respect and honor, serve not only the task of education, but also play an important role in the manifestation of human values and virtues, in the formation of a perfect person plays.

It is known that the development and future of our country depends on achieving high efficiency by making qualitative changes in the field of education, their compatibility with the requirements of world education and to what extent they find their place in practical life.

In our republic, great importance is attached to the creation of sufficient conditions for the harmonious development of children in pre-school educational organizations, and the implementation of innovative and advanced foreign experiences in educational processes. In the "Ilk Kadam" state curriculum, children develop their knowledge of their own "I" and personality traits of others, tolerance and tolerance, social relations and communication in the competences of the field of "Social-emotional development". It is determined that they should master the installation competencies, without applying the concepts of "Pedagogy of Cooperation" and "Tolerance" between the educator and the student, it is impossible to develop a comprehensively developed person.

"Tolerance" is derived from the Latin word "tolerantia" - "tolerance", tolerance, lifestyle, behavior, habits, feelings, opinions, ideas of others. and being tolerant of their beliefs.

The main goal of tolerance is tolerance for young people, respect for representatives of other religions and nations, respect for their values, respect for national wealth, tolerance, tolerance, friendship, brotherhood, patriotism, generosity, loyalty, and respect for others. It consists in forming the skills of looking. The role of educational tools and educators in the education of tolerance in children during preschool education is incomparable, as well as the

concept of tolerance includes the ability to endure, endure, the way of life, thinking, behavior, and values of others. includes concepts such as tolerance, treating them with respect, and not discriminating against others. Today, tolerance is very important. According to this, everyone is free to practice his faith. Everyone should recognize that others also have this right. Uzbekistan is a multi-ethnic country. Along with the Uzbeks, the main nation, more than a hundred nations and peoples with their own culture and traditions live here. In such a situation, the importance of the policy of achieving inter-national and inter-ethnic tolerance in building a multi-ethnic integrated state is extremely high.

In order to fully support tolerance, UNESCO adopted the "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" on November 16, 1995.

Regarding the characteristics of different peoples, nationalities and religions in society the attitude of tolerance can be seen in the example of Uzbekistan. Formation of the concepts of tolerance in the pedagogical processes in young generations is one of the most primary issues facing today's preschool education pedagogy.

Cultivating the attitude of tolerance in the young generation includes the following takes:

1. To explain that all things in the world (continents on the globe, countries, peoples living in them, animals, plants, etc.) are different.
2. To explain that nations have different races, religions, and lifestyles.
3. To explain that nations differ from each other.
4. Be patient and tolerant of differences in people.
5. Teaching citizens to live in peace with each other.
6. Cultivating qualities such as tolerance, patience, endurance in the young generation.

Implementation of the following tasks to educate the attitude of tolerance required:

- to explain to children that people are different, to live with them well, starting from preschool education;
- to explain that everything has unique, valuable properties, so it should be treated with care
- that the culture and lifestyle of his own people is superior to that of others teach not to count;
- deciding to have a tolerant and rational attitude towards the culture, religion, and values of other nations;
- to teach the child to communicate with the surrounding people based on the conditions of mutual understanding, starting from the first kindergarten period;
- instill in children the ability to patiently listen to the opinions of others, encourage them to solve problems on the basis of mutual compromise;
- to teach the basic essence of peace-loving, ethnic, religious, political, confessional (community of people who believe in a particular religion) and interpersonal disagreements, egalitarianism in forming the concepts of tolerance in children.

The need for tolerance has not arisen today. Since ancient times, tolerance has been leading the policy of the kings who conquered many countries. For example, we can clearly see that the ideas of tolerance played a high role in the work of Abu Nasr Farabi, an eastern thinker. His works such as "Treatise on the Ways to Happiness", "Governing the City", "Book on War and

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Peace", "Virtuous Manners", "Views of the Virtuous City People" are imbued with his rich principles of humanity and tolerance. with is important. Pedagogical processes are enriched by the centuries of our great thinkers, the world of science, and the deep meanings of tolerance are conveyed to the young generation by skillful pedagogues, and a tolerant generation will be educated. After all, in all times there was a need for souls nourished by tolerance. Tolerance is of primary importance for all humanity and for an individual, and its importance in the field of international relations is incomparable.

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